

Recommended citation: Ganduri, L., Collier-Reed, B., & Shaw, C. (2021). Digital agency among engineering students post emergence remote teaching. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 232-245). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14646985.

DIGITAL AGENCY AMONG ENGINEERING STUDENTS POST EMERGENCY REMOTE LEARNING

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Conference Key Areas: *Digital Tools; Changes beyond Covid-19*

Keywords: *digital agency, engineering students, educational technology, online learning*

ABSTRACT

The institutionalized transition to virtual classrooms for emergency remote learning caused a shift in the way in which engineering students engage with learning. Before emergency remote learning, many engineering students had limited access to digital technologies for learning. They depended primarily on traditional means of attending face-to-face physical classes and assessments with limited use of blended learning which by definition, involves some online learning. Given the opportunities that online learning provides for students, there is an expectation that post-emergency remote teaching and learning would make use of the online environment. Engineering students must develop their capacity to use and engage with digital technologies, with particular emphasis on the transformative potential of their experiences. This paper makes use of a systematic literature review to describe how engineering students develop their digital agency that is transformative in an online environment by answering the question “How do engineering students develop digital agency in an increasingly online learning environment?”. Data were obtained from research studies

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over the period 2019 to 2021. The qualitative synthesis included 31 studies from the Proquest and Web of Science databases. A thematic analysis of the studies reveals that engineering students develop digital competencies during online learning by accessing key digital technologies, learning approaches, learning environments and, curricula integrated digital frameworks. Further research on the contribution of self-efficacy towards the development of digital agency in an increasingly online learning environment is recommended.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, most engineering students, with very little notice, migrated from conventional classrooms to emergency remote learning (ERL) [1]. Engineering students were required to participate in both synchronous and asynchronous learning activities that were aided by the use of various digital technologies in order to continue with academic activities. Many of the students had limited access to digital technologies prior to the emergency remote learning because they relied primarily on traditional methods of face-to-face lecture delivery and assessment. The primary application of digital technologies, such as learner management systems, was to download content for student access. Because the emergency remote learning was only temporary, engineering faculties appear to be continuing to prioritise online education over classroom learning [1]. Digital technologies that include hardware, applications, and supporting infrastructure have become a requirement for teaching and learning in engineering [2]. Engineering students are expected to study in a variety of virtual learning environments, as well as understand learning analytics and other digital learning applications. They are required to be able to effectively use and manage current and emerging technologies, as well as to adapt related pedagogies to the climate. Students benefit from assessing and managing potential technological advancements, as well as the necessary pedagogical changes, in order to achieve productivity and effectiveness. It is through these activities and responsibilities that engineering students' transformative digital agency becomes relevant for them to learn effectively.

Digital agency is best explained through its various facets. These include digital competence, digital autonomy, digital confidence, and digital accountability [3]. It is further defined as aspects of digital literacy, digital skills, and digital responsibility [3]. To describe digital agency further, a framework to define digital competence based on technological, cognitive, and ethical dimensions was developed [4]. The technological dimension entails being able to approach digital contexts in novel and adaptable ways. Students are expected to use technology primarily as creators rather than consumers to demonstrate their technological competence, seeking out novel ways to use technology to create and share new knowledge. Moreover, the students' ability to critically evaluate digital text and data as well as analyze their relevance and reliability point to their cognitive digital competence. These can carefully consider the sources of digital information and compare and contrast data to reach valid conclusions. When students demonstrate the ability to interact productively with others while using technology responsibly, they are contributing towards the ethical component of digital competence. Integrating these dimensions provide a deeper understanding of the potential offered by technologies that enable students to share information and collaboratively build knowledge [4].

In post-emergency remote learning, one would expect engineering students to acquire all these dimensions of digital competences as they solve challenges presented by interacting with digital resources for online learning. The transformative nature of digital agency is desirable as it assists the students to transfer their interactions with digital resources into an opportunity for learning and development. It avails them of an opportunity to break away from the status quo and changing the situation of the prevailing circumstances [5]. Consequently, students gain control and adapt to a digital world [3]. This study aims to investigate how engineering students develop digital agency in an increasingly online learning environment using a systematic literature review.

1.2 Review question

The qualitative review question “how do engineering students develop digital agency in an increasingly online learning environment?” was developed using the PICO (Population, Phenomenon of Interest and Context) framework. The population consists of engineering students who have abruptly shifted to online learning and are confronted with several challenges associated with the use of technology for learning. The phenomenon is digital agency, and the context is the increasingly online learning environment. Drawing from the theoretical framework on transformative digital agency and through a systematic literature review, this research paper brings an understanding of how engineering students overcome challenges and take control of the use of technology.

1.3 Theoretical Framework

This systematic literature review uses a theoretical framework as an overall orienting lens for the study of digital agency that is transformative among engineering students increasingly online learning environment. The framework is based on Cultural-Historical Activity Theory (CHAT) [6] and Vygotsky’s principle of double stimulation [7]. CHAT has a cultural-historical approach and its foundation is in the work of Russian psychologists, Lev Vygotsky, Alexander Luria and Alexei Leont’ev in the 19th century. The cultural-historical approach effectively investigates how engineering students interact with technology as an activity system for online learning. The students as a group are the primary unit of analysis, while digital tools are the artifacts used for online learning mediation. The historical explanation is spoken of by the multi-voicedness of activity systems and their historicity. Tensions and challenges are used as catalysts for change and development, while the possibility of expansive transformations in activity systems indicates transformative digital agency [6]. In this learning system, digital agency is viewed as an outcome of the system rather than an object [6].

The principle of double stimulation provides a platform for students to engage in volitional actions as they address challenges presented by digital tools during their learning [8]. It contains a first stimulus that represents an issue, a conflict of motives, an obstacle, a difficulty, confusion, or another condition that requires transformative agency to overcome. These largely unknown mechanisms can be investigated by

observing how engineering students respond to the second stimulus or the tools that are mobilized and used in the process of changing their practice. Thus, double stimulation is more than a one-way attempt to appropriate a cultural tool; it is a dialectic and complex activity in which circumstances and agents interact and in unexpected ways. The emerging forms of transformative digital agency can then be explained as resisting change by criticizing, questioning, opposing, or rejecting the activity; explicating new possibilities or potentials in the activity; imagining new patterns or models of the activity; committing to concrete actions aimed at changing the activity and taking consequential actions to change the activity [9].

2 METHODOLOGY

The approach of using a qualitative systematic literature review in engineering education was largely inspired by the work of Borrego [10] and Gough [11]. This approach helped the growing field of engineering education by synthesizing prior work, better informing practice, and identifying important new research directions [10]. The preliminary search, in this case, was conducted using general databases to find relevant articles, ensure the validity of the proposed concept, avoid repetition of previously discussed questions, and ensure the availability of enough articles to conduct the research. This systematic literature review is based on four methods: a systematic search to retrieve relevant articles, systematically applying criteria to code studies for inclusion or exclusion, evaluating study quality, and analyzing review results [10].

2.1 A systematic search

The primary search was conducted using two databases, Web of Science and ProQuest, which were accessed through the [institution name]'s online library between March and April 2021. ProQuest is a searchable indexed database, while Web of Science is an interconnected network of multidisciplinary databases of bibliographic material. These databases were chosen based on the review question and the disciplines that conduct similar studies. The systematic search contained a description of the search concepts, the terms that were used in the search, sources to be searched, and the search limits [11]. Through the assistance of the [Institution name] librarian, the search terms were identified using Boolean logic together with specific keywords as follows: *digital and transformat* (agency or competence or confidence or accountability or literacy or skill* or responsibility) and engineering and education*. Only peer-reviewed journal articles published between 2019 and 2021 were considered. The timeframe includes the period of emergency remote learning, which enabled learnership to continue despite the challenges posed by COVID-19. The preliminary search yielded 4 547 articles.

2.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Following the systematic search, the inclusion criteria were guided by the purpose of the study and the research question for the systematic literature review [10]. As previously stated, peer-reviewed articles accessed through the ProQuest and Web of Science databases and published between 2019 and 2021 were included in the inclusion criteria [10]. However, to be fully part of the inclusion criteria, the articles had to address the research question with subject areas focusing on engineering, education, or educational technology. Furthermore, the exclusion criteria included unrelated, duplicated, inaccessible complete texts, and abstract-only articles. These exclusions were noted and reported in advance to avoid bias by the researchers.

The primary search results were filtered and screened using *engineering, education, or educational technology* subject areas on both the Web of Science and ProQuest databases to determine which papers would meet the inclusion criteria. Papers that did not cover these subject areas were automatically eliminated. As a result, Proquest and Web of Science retained 108 and 24 journal articles respectively with no duplicates. During the second screening process, the 132 articles were further evaluated for relevance to the research question and topic of study. The references were screened based on their key contribution to the use of technology for learning in engineering education, by focusing on the titles of the articles as well as their abstracts. Articles that did not address these issues were deemed unsuitable for the review and were thus omitted. The articles that were excluded focused on, but were not limited to, teachers, elementary or secondary schools, employability, children, workplace education, development or comparison of teaching methods, entrepreneurship, design of digital tools, information technology specialists, and skills other than digital. As a result, 48 journal articles remained in the pool.

3 CRITIQUE AND APPRAISAL

3.1 Appraisal of the quality of the studies

Following the selection, identification, and sorting of primary sources, the next step was to systematically assess the quality of each primary study [10]. The PICo approach, study design, and the year of publication were used to determine eligibility. The use of articles sourced from credible and reputable databases ensures that they are of high quality. The full text of each article was examined for its key contribution to the development of transformative digital agency among engineering students. As a result, articles that focussed on aspects of technology other than agency were excluded (n=15). Furthermore, articles had to be published in English in order for them to be included. This saw two full-text articles published in Russian being excluded. To avoid bias, the remaining 31 peer-reviewed articles were checked to ensure that they all had clearly defined methodologies described. This resulted in 31 articles that were used for the qualitative systematic review. The number of sources included and excluded at each point are tabulated in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews (PRISMA) flowchart (Fig. 1). In addition, Appendix A contains a list of the

peer-reviewed papers (n=31) included in this systematic review, as well as the codes used to identify them using the respective database as a source. The full database for the systematic review can be viewed at: <https://tinyurl.com/SEFIdigitalagency>.

Fig. 1. Systematic search (adapted from PRISMA statement)

3.2 Analysis of the results of the review

The fourth step in conducting a systematic review is to analyze the review's findings. Information about an article's content, what is being researched, and how it is being researched was collected in a standardized format to aid in the analysis of themes and patterns across all of the studies under consideration. The codes outlined in Appendix A were used to describe the findings of the study. The research studies were published in various countries: eleven in Switzerland, seven in the United States of America, five in the United Kingdom, and two in South Africa. Each of the following countries had one publication: Belgium, Egypt, Spain, Turkey, Sweden, West Indies, Morocco, Romania, Austria, Indiana, Singapore, Mauritius and Australia. Six, eighteen, and seven of the 31 peer-reviewed articles were published in 2019, 2020, and 2021, respectively. Looking at these data, it is clear that there was a significant increase in publications on digital literacies from 2020, which can be explained by the implementation of emergency remote learning in early 2020. Table 1 depicts the distribution of journals in which the articles under consideration were published. Sustainability has the most articles (n=7), followed by Education Sciences (n=4).

Table 1. Articles per Journal

Journal	Papers Per Journal
EAI Endorsed Transactions on Creative Technologies	1
Education & Training	1
Education Sciences	4
Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning	1
Information Technology & People	1
International Journal of Education and Information Technologies	1
International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education	2
International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy	1
International Journal of Game-Based Learning	1
International Journal of STEM Education	1
International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing	2
Journal of Engineering	1
Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice	1
Journal of Physics: Conference Series	2
South African Journal of Industrial Engineering	1
South African Journal of Science	1
Sustainability	7
The Electronic Library	1
The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology	1

A variety of research designs and methods were found to have been used across the studies. The most common research design (n=13) was a literature review, with five based on a systematic literature review and one combined with a survey. There are six surveys, five evaluation studies and two case studies. The intervention method, multimethod design, phenomenography, process approach method, and a quasi-experimental study were also found. These research designs were uniformly divided into qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods. Furthermore, data collection methods reported ranged from using the PRISMA statement in systematic literature reviews to using questionnaires and interviews in surveys.

The collected data for this research were aggregated, integrated, and interpreted to determine the evidence considered to answer the review question. Several themes emerged from an analysis of the data and are presented in the next section. The majority of the articles addressed the challenges presented by the shift in technological advancement caused by COVID-19 or Industry 4.0, and described how engineering students must adapt to the digital skills demand placed on them. Other articles highlighted the need for faculties of engineering to intervene and assist students to develop competences in digital technology as required. The study's main limitations were the low number of databases and articles used for the review.

4 RESULTS

The aggregated results of the systematic review are divided into 5 themes: results that foreground engineering students' access to educational technology (ET), results that foreground self-efficacy (SE), results that point to the need for specific learning approaches (LAs), results that foreground the learning environment (LE), and lastly, results that suggest integration of digital frameworks into the curriculum (IC). These are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Themes

Themes	Theme Code	Paper Code	<i>n</i>
Access to Technology	ET	1P, 6P, 7P, 8P, 10P, 13P, 14P, 17P, 18P, 19P, 22P, 23P, 27W, 28W, 30W, 31W	16
Self-efficacy	SE	6P, 10P, 19P, 30W	4
Learning Approaches	LAs	4P, 5P, 11P, 14P, 20P, 23P, 24P, 26W, 27W, 29W	10
Learning Environment	LE	8P, 9P, 13P, 14P, 16P, 17P, 18P, 19P, 25P, 31W	10
Intergration of digital frameworks into Curricula	IC	10P, 12P, 13P, 14P, 15P, 16P, 18P,	7

4.1 Access to educational technology (ET): *n* = 16

Access to key educational technology (ET) for engineering students was recommended in more than half of the articles as a way for engineering students to develop their digital agency, as shown in Table 2. Educational or collaborative robotics [1P, 2P, 7P, 18P], open-access tools, applications, software [30W], smart classrooms [17P], Artificial Intelligence (AI), 3D-printing [13P, 18P], human interfaces, augmented and virtual reality systems [27W] are examples of key and high-performing educational technology. Emerging from the analysis we suggest that for engineering students to develop their digital literacy, they require not only physical access to technology, but also technical support [8P], endogenous motivational access, skills access, actual usage of digital technologies [7P], and practical expertise [13P], among other things. We also argue that investing in these technologies will primarily benefit non-Generation Z students [28W]. These students must be able to access pedagogy remotely when necessary, using distance digital tools such as video conferencing tools [14P, 30W]. Overall, engineering students' digital competences are enhanced when they have access to guided inquiry or training [8P, 19P] and mentorship on how to creatively use the emerging and old technologies [10P, 22P]. According to Aagaard and Lund[5], digital agency that is transformative is developed when students interact with these digital resources.

4.2 Self-efficacy (SE): $n = 4$

Four articles specifically mention self-efficacy as a way for engineering students to develop their digital agency (see Table 2). Students' ability to control their use of technology can be seen when they adapt to using not only low-level technology but also high-level technology such as 3D platforms, AI applications, and mobile phones, among other things [6P]. The more engineering students utilise these technologies, the more they develop digital skills and related competences. Digital skills are further developed as students understand both hardware and software for online learning [10P], virtual collaborations [8P], training or adoption of engaging new technologies such as blogs [19P, 23P], and mastering distance tools such as video conferencing tools [30W]. Furthermore, students must be willing to embrace technological innovation in order to realize their full potential [31W].

4.3 Learning Approaches (LAs) : $n = 10$

Exposure to a variety of learning approaches can assist students to develop digital agency [4P, 5P]. Student-centred approaches, such as active learning, have been shown to provide students with hands-on experience with technology [4P, 5P]. Some of the learning approaches recommended as a result of this research are challenge-based learning [26W], game-based learning [11P, 29W], innovative approaches [14P], industry collaboration [24P], skills development approaches like high-tech labs, education 4.0 or learning factories [20P]. It is further argued that as students adopt these learning processes they, in turn, develop their digital skills [23P]. Accessing online in-game guidance that is constantly updated, as well as adequate technological support, can expedite the process.

4.4 Learning Environment (LE) : $n = 10$

Apart from the learning approaches adopted by students, the systematic literature review suggests that a supportive learning environment positively contributes to the development of students' digital agency [13P]. This includes constructivist learning environments, such as makerspaces, which provide hands-on experience with the use of technology for learning [8P]. Furthermore, the results suggest that experiential learning and integrated learning environments increase student confidence as they use educational technologies [9P]. As a result, there is a push for universities to modernize engineering programs, develop smart education, and promote active learning environments [31W], as well as facilities and infrastructure that support the acquisition of digital skills, such as the learning factory and education 4.0 [16P, 18P]. Rapid digital transformation at the institutional level has a significant impact on engineering students' acquisition of digital competencies.

However, it is also important to note that the cultural, societal and demographic aspects play a role in every learning environment. As a result, institutions must promote the use of digital technologies not only within their own circles, but also at the most elementary levels.

4.5 Integration of digital frameworks into the curricula (IC): $n = 7$

Exposing engineering students to various digital frameworks as they progress through their programmes can aid in the development of digital agencies [10P]. This is made possible by revising or modifying engineering programmes, forming partnerships with industry [13P], incorporating the internet of things into pedagogical models [15P], and incorporating digital frameworks such as education 4.0, big data, advanced simulation, learning factory 4.0, and virtual reality. Engineering students become acquainted with these digital frameworks while carrying out their daily tasks.

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APPENDIX A

Table A1. Codification of Peer-Reviewed Articles included in the Systematic Review

CODE	YEAR	TITLE	JOURNAL NAME	CITATION
1P	2021	Implementation of Educational Robotic into Teaching-Learning Process to Enhance Students Skills in the Science and Technology	Journal of Physics: Conference Series	Huda, S., Zuhrie, M. S., Buditjahjanto, I. G. P. A., & Nurlaela, L. (2021, March). Implementation of Educational Robotic into Teaching-Learning Process to Enhance Students Skills in the Science and Technology. In Journal of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 1842, No. 1, p. 012062). IOP Publishing.
2P	2021	Self-efficacy and belonging: the impact of a university makerspace	International Journal of STEM Education	Andrews, M. E., Borrego, M., & Boklage, A. (2021). Self-efficacy and belonging: the impact of a university makerspace. International Journal of STEM Education, 8(1), 1-18.
3P	2021	Implementation of Digital Games in Advancing Students' Higher-Order Thinking Skills: A Review	Journal of Physics: Conference Series	Ahmad, M., Mansor, N. R., Rashid, R. A., Ain, N., Zakaria, C. R., & Sung, C. M. (2021, February). Implementation of Digital Games in Advancing Students' Higher-Order Thinking Skills: A Review. In Journal of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 1793, No. 1, p. 012069). IOP Publishing.
4P	2021	Mechatronics: Experiential Learning and the Stimulation of Thinking Skills	Education Sciences	Habib, M. K., Nagata, F., & Watanabe, K. (2021). Mechatronics: Experiential Learning and the Stimulation of Thinking Skills. Education Sciences, 11(2), 46.
5P	2021	Challenges of Active Learning in a View of Integrated Engineering Education	Education Sciences	Vodovozov, V., Raud, Z., & Petlenkov, E. (2021). Challenges of Active Learning in a View of Integrated Engineering Education. Education Sciences, 11(2), 43.
6P	2021	Skills for a Working Future: How to Bring about Professional Success from the Educational Setting	Education Sciences	García-Pérez, L., García-Garnica, M., & Olmedo-Moreno, E. M. (2021). Skills for a Working Future: How to Bring about Professional Success from the Educational Setting. Education Sciences, 11(1), 27.
7P	2020	Digital divide among higher education faculty: Revista de Universidad y Sociedad del Conocimiento	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education	Soomro, K. A., Kale, U., Curtis, R., Akcaoglu, M., & Bernstein, M. (2020). Digital divide among higher education faculty. International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education, 17, 1-16.
8P	2020	Making Future-Ready Students with Design and the Internet of Things	EAI Endorsed Transactions on Creative Technologies	Hughes, J., Robb, J. A., & Lam, M. (2020). Making Future-Ready Students with Design and the Internet of Things. EAI Endorsed Transactions on Creative Technologies, 6(21).
9P	2020	Experiential and Integrated Learning Environments - Teaching Urban Design Studio at Curtin University	Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice	Mancini, F., & Glusac, T. (2020). Experiential and Integrated Learning Environments-Teaching Urban Design Studio at Curtin University. Journal of Higher Education Theory & Practice, 20(9).
10P	2020	Key competencies for big data analytics professions: a multimethod study	Information Technology & People	Persaud, A. (2020). Key competencies for big data analytics professions: a multimethod study. Information Technology & People.
11P	2020	The Transportability of a Game-Based Learning Approach to Undergraduate Mechanical Engineering Education: Effects on Student Conceptual Understanding, Engagement, and Experience	Sustainability	Shernoff, D. J., Ryu, J. C., Ruzek, E., Coller, B., & Prantil, V. (2020). The Transportability of a Game-Based Learning Approach to Undergraduate Mechanical Engineering Education: Effects on Student Conceptual Understanding, Engagement, and Experience. Sustainability, 12(17), 6986.
12P	2020	The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a Basis for Innovation Skills for Engineers in the Industry 4.0 Context	Sustainability	Rivera, M. L., Hermosilla, P., Delgadillo, J., & Echeverría, D. (2020). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a Basis for Innovation Skills for Engineers in the Industry 4.0 Context. Sustainability, 12(16), 6622.

CODE	YEAR	TITLE	JOURNAL NAME	CITATION
13P	2020	Adapting Universities for Sustainability Education in Industry 4.0: Channel of Challenges and Opportunities	Sustainability	Mian, S. H., Salah, B., Ameen, W., Moiduddin, K., & Alkhalefah, H. (2020). Adapting Universities for Sustainability Education in Industry 4.0: Channel of Challenges and Opportunities. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(15), 6100.
14P	2020	Graduate Employability and Competence Development in Higher Education—A Systematic Literature Review Using PRISMA	Sustainability	Abelha, M., Fernandes, S., Mesquita, D., Seabra, F., & Ferreira-Oliveira, A. T. (2020). Graduate Employability and Competence Development in Higher Education—A Systematic Literature Review Using PRISMA. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(15), 5900.
15P	2020	The Technological Challenge Facing Higher Education Professors: Perceptions of ICT Tools for Developing 21st Century Skills	Sustainability	Liesa-Orús, M., Latorre-Cosculluela, C., Vázquez-Toledo, S., & Sierra-Sánchez, V. (2020). The technological challenge facing higher education professors: Perceptions of ICT tools for developing 21st century skills. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(13), 5339.
16P	2020	Model Proposal for Diagnosis and Integration of Industry 4.0 Concepts in Production Engineering Courses	Sustainability	Souza, R. G. D., & Quelhas, O. L. G. (2020). Model Proposal for Diagnosis and Integration of Industry 4.0 Concepts in Production Engineering Courses. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(8), 3471.
17P	2020	The Smart Classroom as a Means to the Development of ESD Methodologies	Sustainability	Cebrián, G., Palau, R., & Mogas, J. (2020). The smart classroom as a means to the development of ESD methodologies. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(7), 3010.
18P	2020	Exponential Disruptive Technologies and the Required Skills of Industry 4.0	Journal of Engineering	Bongomin, O., Gilibrays Ocen, G., Oyondi Nganyi, E., Musinguzi, A., & Omara, T. (2020). Exponential disruptive technologies and the required skills of industry 4.0. <i>Journal of Engineering</i> , 2020.
19P	2020	Mapping research in student engagement and educational technology in higher education: a systematic evidence map: Revista de Universidad y Sociedad del Conocimiento	International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education	Bond, M., Buntins, K., Bedenlier, S., Zawacki-Richter, O., & Kerres, M. (2020). Mapping research in student engagement and educational technology in higher education: A systematic evidence map. <i>International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education</i> , 17(1), 2.
20P	2019	An Investigation of Industry 4.0 Skills Requirements	South African Journal of Industrial Engineering	Maisiri, W., Darwish, H., & van Dyk, L. (2019). An investigation of industry 4.0 skills requirements. <i>South African Journal of Industrial Engineering</i> , 30(3), 90-105.
21P	2019	Effects of digital flipped classroom teaching method integrated cooperative learning model on learning motivation and outcome	The Electronic Library	Qiang, J. (2018). Effects of digital flipped classroom teaching method integrated cooperative learning model on learning motivation and outcome. <i>Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education</i> , 14(6), 2213-2220
22P	2019	Creativity and Emerging Digital Educational Technologies: A Systematic Review	TOJET : The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology	Yalcinalp, S., & Avci, Ü. (2019). Creativity and Emerging Digital Educational Technologies: A Systematic Review. <i>Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology-TOJET</i> , 18(3), 25-45.
23P	2019	The ecosystem of e-learning model for higher education	South African Journal of Science	van de Heyde, V., & Siebrits, A. (2019). The ecosystem of e-learning model for higher education. <i>South African Journal of Science</i> , 115(5-6), 1-6.
24P	2019	Students' learning experience in a multidisciplinary innovation project	Education & Training	Hero, L. M., & Lindfors, E. (2019). Students' learning experience in a multidisciplinary innovation project. <i>Education+ Training</i> .

CODE	YEAR	TITLE	JOURNAL NAME	CITATION
25P	2019	Supporting Project-Based Learning through Economical and Flexible Learning Spaces	Education Sciences	Eickholt, J., Jogiparthi, V., Seeling, P., Hinton, Q., & Johnson, M. (2019). Supporting project-based learning through economical and flexible learning spaces. <i>Education Sciences</i> , 9(3), 212.
26W	2020	An artificial intelligence educational strategy for the digital transformation	International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing	Cantú-Ortiz, F. J., Sánchez, N. G., Garrido, L., Terashima-Marin, H., & Brena, R. F. (2020). An artificial intelligence educational strategy for the digital transformation. <i>International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)</i> , 14(4), 1195-1209.
27W	2020	Exploring technology attitudes and personal-cultural orientations as student readiness factors for digitalised work	Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning	Blayone, T. J., Mykhailenko, O., Usca, S., Abuze, A., Romanets, I., & Oleksiiv, M. (2020). Exploring technology attitudes and personal-cultural orientations as student readiness factors for digitalised work. <i>Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning</i> .
28W	2020	Educational experiences with Generation Z	International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)	Hernandez-de-Menendez, M., Díaz, C. A. E., & Morales-Menendez, R. (2020). Educational experiences with Generation Z. <i>International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)</i> , 14(3), 847-859.
29W	2020	Game Jams for Learning and Teaching: A Review	International Journal of Game-Based Learning	Meriläinen, M., Aurava, R., Kultima, A., & Stenros, J. (2020). Game jams for learning and teaching: a review. <i>International Journal of Game-Based Learning (IJGBL)</i> , 10(2), 54-71.
30W	2020	Remote Knowledge Acquisition and Assessment During the COVID-19 Pandemic	International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (iJEP)	Jacques, S., Ouahabi, A., & Lequeu, T. (2020). Remote Knowledge Acquisition and Assessment During the COVID-19 Pandemic. <i>International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (iJEP)</i> , 10.
31W	2019	Establishment of smart education system in modern universities: concept, technologies and challenges	International Journal of Education And Information Technologies	Salem, A. M., Mikhalkina, E. V. and Nikitaeva, A. Y. (2019). Establishment of smart education system in modern universities: concept, technologies and challenges. <i>International Journal of Education and Information Technologies</i> . (13), 180-188